

Indantrones from 1-Aminoanthraquinones. Part II. Mechanism of Indanthrone Formation from 1-Aminoanthraquinone

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An ionic mechanism is suggested for the formation of indanthrone from 1-aminoanthraquinone by the reaction of potassium hydroxide in dimethyl sulphoxide or tetramethylurea.

1-Aminoanthraquinone gave 1-amino-2-toluidino-anthraquinone when reacted with *p*-toluidine and potassium hydroxide in dimethyl sulphoxide. 1'-Amino-1, 2'-dianthrimide cyclised to indanthrone with potassium hydroxide in dimethyl sulphoxide ; its *N*-methyl derivative, however, did not yield an indanthrone derivative under identical conditions.

When 1-aminoanthraquinone was reacted with potassium hydroxide and *p*-nitrobenzylbromide in tetramethylurea, in nitrogen atmosphere, a tetrasubstituted leuco derivative of indanthrone was obtained.

INDANTHRONE (I) can be prepared in good yields from 1-aminoanthraquinone (II a) by the reaction of alkali hydroxide in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO),¹ or tetramethylurea (TMU)². If this reaction is carried out at 60°, the reaction product contains mainly indanthrone

and unreacted 1-aminoanthraquinone³. The conversion of indanthrone can be increased to 70% by the addition of anthracene to the reaction mixture³. In this paper the mechanism of this reaction has been elucidated.

I

III

- II
a, (R₁ = NH₂, R₂ = H)
b, (R₁ = NH₂, R₂ = OH)
c, (R₁ = NH₂, R₂ = NHC₆H₄-*p*)
d, (R₁ = NH₂, R₂ = Br)

IV

V

Substitution in 1-aminoanthraquinone: 1-Aminoanthraquinone substitutes mainly in the 2-position under these reaction conditions. When 1-aminoanthraquinone reacts with potassium hydroxide and cupric chloride in DMSO, 1-amino-2-hydroxyanthraquinone (II b) is obtained in 37% yield and indanthrone in 10% yield⁸. 1-Amino-2-anilino- or 2-*p*-toluidino-(IIc)-anthraquinones were obtained as major products when 1-aminoanthraquinone reacted with aniline or *p*-toluidine and alkali in DMSO. The constitution of the product (II c) was proved by its conversion to the triazole (III) on treatment with nitrous acid.

1-Aminoanthraquinone as a substituting agent:

1-Aminoanthraquinone also replaces nuclear hydrogen in aromatic compounds containing carbonyl groups, e. g., benzanthrone (IV) and anthraisothiazolone (V) when reacted with 1-aminoanthraquinone and alkali in DMSO yield (VI)⁴ and (VII)⁵ respectively.

1-Aminoanthraquinone therefore may react with itself to give 1'-amino-1, 2'-dianthrimide. Earlier patents claim its cyclisation to indanthrone with acidic and alkaline reagents⁶. Venkataraman⁷ has wrongly pictured this cyclisation as involving the loss of ammonia.

1'-Amino-1, 2'-dianthrimide (VIII a) could not be prepared by the condensation of 1-amino-2-bromoanthraquinone (II d) with 1-aminoanthraquinone as claimed in a patent.⁸ Under mild conditions, no reaction took place; only indanthrone was obtained under vigorous conditions. 1-Benzamido-2-bromoanthraquinone did not condense with 1-aminoanthraquinone. It (VIII a) was prepared by the condensation of 1-phthalimido-2-bromoanthraquinone with 1-aminoanthraquinone and subsequent hydrolysis of the phthalimido group. It cyclised to indanthrone with potassium hydroxide in DMSO.

The methylation of (VIIIa) did not yield a homogeneous N-methyl derivative (VIII b); the latter compound was prepared by benzoylation of VIIIa, followed by methylation and subsequent debenzoylation. It did not cyclise to yield an indanthrone derivative, with potassium hydroxide in DMSO.

When 1-aminoanthraquinone was allowed to react with *p* nitrobenzylbromide and potassium hydroxide in TMU, under nitrogen atmosphere, a tetrasubstituted reduced derivative of indanthrone (IX) was obtained. Indanthrone was unaffected under these conditions indicating that N-substitution did not take place under these conditions.

Brunner and Deffner⁹ have recently shown that a mixture of 1-aminoanthraquinone, DMSO and a base shows the presence of semiquinone radicals according to ESR spectra. Venkataraman¹⁰ states that a mixture of 1-aminoanthraquinone, potassium hydroxide and TMU also exhibits strong free radical ESR signal which is indefinitely stable so that a radical mechanism might be involved; however specific radical intermediates could not be identified and indanthrone itself exhibits free radical ESR signal.

The intermediate is likely to be a radical anion as the reaction involves an alkaline condensing agent. In the radical anion formation, the ESR is sufficiently detailed to permit an independent identification.¹¹ It appears that at low temperature, the less reactive semiquinone radicals are present.

The reaction can be carried out in nitrogen atmosphere and addition of anthracene, a radical trapping agent¹², can be used for improving the conversion to indanthrone.³ So the reaction is possibly ionic in character. This is supported by the fact that the addition to the reaction mixture of cupric chloride, a reagent favouring anionic reactions, yields indanthrone, a coupling product side by side with 1-amino-2-hydroxyanthraquinone, a substitution product.⁸ Bradley¹³ has recorded many such instances in anionic reactions in polycyclic ketones. No indanthrone could be isolated when oxygen, a radical forming reagent, was passed in

the reaction mixture of 1-amino-anthraquinone and caustic potash in DMSO throughout³.

The ionic mechanism is indicated in the chart. 1-Aminoanthraquinone when reacted with potassium hydroxide gives an enol represented as an anion (X). Addition of X to the quinone system of 1-aminoanthraquinone gives XI and dianion XII. Oxidation of

XII gives VIIIa, which cyclises to indanthrone by repetition of the process. A repetition of hydrogen migration from XII gives XIII. Formation of XIII and XIV are responsible for the non-cyclisation of methylated anthrimide (VIII b). Formation of XV explains the tetrasubstituted derivative of reduced indanthrone with *p*-nitrobenzylbromide. Thus the suggested mechanism explains all the experimental facts mentioned.

Experimental

1-Amino-2-toluidino-anthraquinone: A mixture of 1-aminoanthraquinone (1 g.), DMSO (10ml.), *p*-toluidine (5 g.) and potassium hydroxide (2 g.) was stirred at 60° for 6 hr. The product (0.9 g.) was collected after diluting it with water and acidifying with hydrochloric acid. The acetone soluble product (0.7 g.) was collected after Soxhlet extraction with acetone. Its solution in trichloroethylene was chromatographed on basic alumina. It separated into five fractions on alumina. The first weakly adsorbed orange fraction and the second violet fractions were the major ones. The strongly adsorbed greenish blue, dull reddish blue, and the black fractions were the minor ones. The orange band was eluted with pure trichloroethylene and contained unreacted 1-aminoanthraquinone (0.2 g.). The next band was also eluted with trichloroethylene and on concentration gave violet needles with metallic lustre (0.3 g.) which melted at 262°. (Found: C, 76.6; H, 5.0; N, 8.3%. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_2$, C, 76.8; H, 4.9; N, 8.5%.)

The violet product dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with deep blue colour and in acetone with red colour. Its red pyridine solution on dilution with methanolic potassium hydroxide turned green.

The acetone insoluble residue was extracted with dimethyl formamide (DMF). The DMF insoluble residue (0.2 g.) on chromatography and crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave blue needles with metallic lustre of indanthrone.

1-Amino-2-anilino-anthraquinone: The above experiment was repeated using aniline instead of *p*-toluidine and worked up in the same manner. The compound melted at 256°. (Found: C, 76.6; H, 4.4; N, 8.6%. Calcd for $C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_2$, C, 76.4; H, 4.5; N, 8.9%.)

3-*p*-Tolyl-anthra-(1, 2-*d*) triazole (III): The 1-amino-2-toluidino-anthraquinone (0.3 g.) was boiled with glacial acetic acid (30 ml) and the solution after cooling to 5°, was added with stirring to an icecold solution of sodium nitrite (1g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (12 ml) dropwise. After the addition, the mixture was stirred for 40 mins. at 5°. It was then added to the boiling alcohol (40 ml) containing copper sulphate (0.2 g.) and the alcoholic mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. It was diluted with water and the precipitate was collected. Crystallisation from chlorobenzene gave pale green needles (0.1 g.), m. p. 322°. Found: C, 74.2; H, 4.0; N, 12.2%. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{15}N_3O_2$, C, 74.3; H, 3.9; N, 12.4%.)

It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with greenish yellow colour.

Attempted synthesis of 1'-amino-1,2'-dianthrimide:

(a) A mixture of 1-amino-2-bromo-anthraquinone (3 g.), 1-aminoanthraquinone (2.2 g.), anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.1 g.), copper bronze (0.1 g.) and amyl alcohol (20 ml) were refluxed for 10 hr. The reaction product was collected in the usual manner. It was completely soluble in acetone and did not contain any aminodanthrimide.

(b) The above reaction when carried out in nitrobenzene instead of amyl alcohol at reflux gave mainly indanthrone and no aminodanthrimide could be isolated.

(c) 1-Benzamido-2-bromo-anthraquinone¹⁴ did not condense with 1-aminoanthraquinone in nitrobenzene or DMF under Ullmann's conditions.

1-Phthalimido-2-bromo-anthraquinone: A mixture of 1-amino-2-bromoanthraquinone (1 g.), phthalic anhydride (5g.) and a few drops of pyridine was refluxed for 90 min. and the product (1.2 g.) was collected after diluting the reaction mixture with water. It crystallised from benzene in yellow plates, m. p. 250° (Found: Br, 18.5%. Calcd for $C_{22}H_{10}BrNO_4$, Br, 18.5%).

1'-Phthalimido-1, 2'-dianthrimide: A mixture of 1-phthalimido-2-bromo-anthraquinone (2 g.), 1-aminoanthraquinone (1 g.), anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.2 g.), copper bronze (0.1 g.), naphthalene (10 g.) and a few drops of xylene was refluxed for 6 hr. A brown product (2 g.) was collected after steam distillation. Crystallisation from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave red needles, m. p. 329°. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 3.5; N, 4.9%. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{18}N_2O_6$, C, 75.3; H, 3.1; N, 4.9%.)

The red product dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with blue colour and did not dye cotton from red alkaline dithionite vat.

1'-Amino-1, 2'-dianthrimide: A mixture of the above compound (1 g.), ethyl alcohol (25 ml), and hydrazine hydrate (3 ml. of 85%) was refluxed for 3 hr. and a brown product (0.8 g) was collected after diluting it with water. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave dark brown needles. (Found: C, 75.7; H, 4.0; N, 6.7%. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{18}N_2O_4$, C, 75.7; H, 3.6; N, 6.3%.)

It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with deep blue colour. Its pink solution in pyridine changed to green on addition of methanolic potassium hydroxide. It did not dye cotton from pinkish brown alkaline dithionite vat.

It (1 g.) gave indanthrone (0.7 g.) when reacted with alkaline potassium hydroxide in DMSO in the usual manner.

1'-Benzamido-1, 2'-dianthrimide: The above product (2 g.), benzoyl chloride (8 ml) and *o*-dichlorobenzene (15 ml.) were refluxed for 3 hr. and the product (1.5 g) was collected after dilution with ethanol. Crystallisation from acetic acid gave brown needles, m. p., 297°. (Found: C, 76.6; H, 4.0; N, 4.8%. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_5$, C, 76.6; H, 3.6; N, 5.1%.)

It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with blue colour. Its pinkish brown pyridine solution turned dirty green on addition of methanolic potassium hydroxide.

1'-Benzoylmethylamino-N-methyl-1, 2'-dianthrimide

The above product (1.4 g.), methyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (5 ml.), dry potassium carbonate (0.8 g.) and *o*-dichlorobenzene (15 ml.) were refluxed for 3 hr. The suspension was filtered. The filtrate on concentration gave orange precipitate (1.1 g.). Its solution in chlorobenzene on chromatography on alumina and subsequent concentration of the least adsorbed fraction gave red needles, m. p. 327°. (Found : C, 76.8 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 4.4%. Calcd. for $C_{37}H_{24}N_2O_5$, C, 77.1 ; H, 4.1 ; N, 4.8%.)

1'-Methylamino-N-methyl-1, 2'-dianthrimide : The above product (1 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml.) at 100° for 10 min. A blue product (0.9 g.) was collected after dilution with water. Crystallisation from aniline gave blue needles. (Found : C, 76.0 ; H, 4.2%. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{20}N_2O_4$, C, 76.3 ; H, 4.2%.)

It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with yellowish brown colour. It did not dye cotton from red alkaline dithionite vat. It gave the starting material on rebenzoylation and did not yield an indanthrone derivative when reacted with potassium hydroxide in DMSO.

Synthesis of IX : A mixture of 1-aminoanthraquinone (2 g.), TMU (15 ml.), potassium hydroxide (4 g.) was stirred at 55° for 6 hr. under nitrogen atmosphere. Then *p*-nitrobenzylbromide (4 g.) and potassium hydroxide (2 g.) were added. The reaction was continued for 2 hr. more. A brown product (4 g.) was collected after dilution with water. It was freed of acetone solubles. Acetone insoluble residue was Soxhlet extracted with DMF. The DMF extracts were precipitated by water. (Found : C, 68.6 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 8.3%. Calcd. for $C_{56}H_{38}N_6O_{12}$, C, 68.2 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 8.5%.)

It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with brown colour. It did not vat with alkaline dithionite.

Indanthrone did not react under the above reaction conditions.

References

1. CASSELLA FARBERWERKE MAINKUR A-G, French Patent, 1964, 1, 376, 198 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 62, 13282.
2. W. ZERWECK and E. SCHWAMBERGER (to Cassella Farberwerke Mainkur A-G), German Patent, 1966, 1, 264, 648 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 68, 115699 f.
3. MISS M. K. SHAH and K. H. SHAH, *Indian J. Technol.*, 1975, 13, 312.
4. W. ZERWECK and E. SCHWAMBERGER (to Cassella Farberwerke Mainkur A-G), German Patent, 1962, 1, 171, 441 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 61, 6974, e.
5. A. S. KAJI, K. H. SHAH and K. M. SHAH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 6, 613.
6. BADISCHE ANILIN and SODA FABRIK, German Patent, 1907, 1, 98, 025 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1908, 2, 2454.
7. K. VENKATARAMAN, "The Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes". Vol. II, Academic Press, 1952, p. 933.
8. Farben fabriken vorm Friedr. Bayer, German Patent, 1910, 240, 276 ; Friendlaender, *Forteschritte der Teerfarben fabrikation*, 1910, 2, 696.
9. K. BRUNNER and U. DEFFNER, *Melliand Textilber*, 1969, 50, 437.
10. K. VENKATARAMAN, "The Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes", Vol. V. Academic Press, 1971, p. 184.
11. H. C. R. SYMONS IN GOLD'S, *Advances in Physical Organic Chemistry*", Vol. 1, Academic Press, 1963, p. 289.
12. K. C. BASS and G. N. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc. C*, 1971, 1.
13. W. BRADLEY, "Recent Progress in the Chemistry of Dyes and Pigments", The Royal Institute of Chemistry, Monograph, 1958, No 5 p. 19.
14. ANGELO MANGINI and BRUNO WEGER, *Chem. Abs.*, 1945, 39, 417.